

**ASSESSING THE EFFICIENCY OF TRANSFORMERS BASED ON
EFFICIENCY COEFFICIENT AND ENERGY LOSSES AND
OPTIMIZING THEIR OPERATING MODE**

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Abstract

The article analyzes the factors affecting the energy losses and efficiency coefficient (EC) of high-capacity transformers and the causes of these losses. Based on the analysis results, the efficiency of transformers is evaluated, and their optimal operating modes are presented.

Introduction

Reducing energy losses in power transformers is one of the pressing issues in the energy sector. Transformers play a vital role in the transmission, distribution, and delivery of electrical energy to consumers. During operation, energy losses lead to decreased supply efficiency, increased costs, and negative environmental impact.

Energy losses in transformers

Power losses in transformers are divided into two main types:

- Magnetic losses occur in the core during the magnetization process under the influence of alternating magnetic flux.
- Electrical losses result from the current passing through the winding conductors and converting into heat according to Joule's law.

Electrical losses

Electrical losses are the energy converted into heat due to current flow in transformer windings. The power consumed for electrical losses (P_e) is proportional to the square of the current and includes the sum of the electrical losses of the primary (P_{e1}) and secondary (P_{e2}) windings:

$$P_e = P_{e1} + P_{e2} = mI_1^2 r_1 + mI_2^2 r_2$$

where m is the number of transformer phases.

When the no-load loss equals the electrical loss, the efficiency coefficient reaches its maximum value. Electrical losses are calculated for the nominal currents of the windings based on short-circuit parameters:

$$P_0 = \beta^2 P_{KT},$$

where β is the load coefficient. Electrical losses are variable and depend on transformer loading.

Magnetic losses in a transformer occur due to the magnetization of the magnetic core (magnetic conductor) under alternating magnetic field over time.

Two types of magnetic losses occur during magnetization:

- Hysteresis losses P_G : energy used to compensate for residual magnetization.
- Eddy current losses P_{UT} : energy dissipated as heat in the magnetic core plates under alternating magnetic field.

$$P_M = P_G + P_{UT}$$

To reduce magnetic energy losses, the transformer magnetic core is made of thin ferromagnetic plates (electrical steel), insulated with technical varnish and firmly stacked.

Frequency dependence of magnetic losses:

Hysteresis losses are directly proportional to the magnetization frequency ($P_G \sim f$), and eddy current losses are proportional to the square of the frequency ($P_{UT} \equiv f^2$).

Magnetic losses also depend on the magnetic induction in the core and its connections ($P_m \sim B$). At constant primary voltage ($U_1 = \text{const}$), magnetic losses remain constant and do not depend on transformer load.

When designing a transformer, magnetic losses are determined P_{sol} by specific magnetic losses for 1 kg of electrical steel at 1.0 or 1.5 T magnetic induction and 50 Hz frequency.

$$P_M = P_{sol} (B/B)^2 (f/50)^{1.3} G$$

[Graph 1. Relationship between transformer loss and load]

Where: B - actual magnetic induction in transformer core (TL). B_{sol} - magnetic induction for specific magnetic losses; G - core weight (kg)

Magnetic losses are determined by no-load test at constant voltage.

Energy balance equation of transformer

The energy supplied to the primary winding from the grid is partially lost as electrical loss P_{e1} , and the alternating magnetic flux in the transformer core causes magnetic loss (P_{em}). The remaining power is transferred to the secondary winding as electromagnetic power $P_{em} = P_{e1} - P_{e2} - P_m$, where part of it is lost as electrical loss P_{e2} and the rest is delivered to the load: $P_2 = P_1 - \sum P$ where: $\sum P = P_{e1} + P_{e2} + P_m$

Efficiency coefficient is the ratio of active power delivered to the load from the secondary winding to the power supplied to the primary winding from the grid:

$$\eta = \frac{P_2}{P_1} = \left(\frac{P_1 - \sum P}{P_1} \right) = 1 - \frac{\sum P}{P_1}$$

$P_2 = P_0 + \beta^2 P_{kt}$ the power wasted when the transformer is operating at idle and under load.

The output active power at the secondary winding:

$$P_2 = \sqrt{3} U_2 I_2 \cos \varphi_2 = \beta * S_{nom} \cos \varphi_2$$

$$S_{nom} = \sqrt{3} U_{2N} I_{2N} - \text{transformer rated capacity (kVA)}$$

U_{2N}, I_{2N} – line voltage and current values.

If we write the power supplied to the transformer as follows,

$$P_1 = P_2 + \sum P$$

Efficiency coefficient expression:

$$\eta = \frac{P_2}{P_1} = \frac{\beta * S_{nom} \cos \varphi_2}{\beta * S_{nom} \cos \varphi_2 + P_0 + \beta^2 P_K}$$

It can be seen from the expression that the transformer F.I.K. depends on the nature of the transformer load ($\cos \varphi_2$), the amount of loading (β).

Figure 2. Transformer F.I.K. load dependence graph.

As can be seen from the graph, the maximum value of F.I.K. is achieved when the electrical and magnetic losses are equal.

$$P_0 = \beta^2 / P_k$$

From this we determine the loading coefficient

$$\beta' = \sqrt{P_0 / P_k}$$

Typically, the F.I.K. of a transformer is achieved when the load factor is equal to $\beta' = 0,45 \div 0,65$

The maximum value of the F.I.K. of a transformer is found by the following formula.

$$\eta = \frac{\beta * S_{nom} \cos \varphi_2}{\beta * S_{nom} \cos \varphi_2 + 2P_0}$$

The effect of residual work loss and electrical losses.

Residual work loss exists even when the transformer is not connected to a load and is caused by the overmagnetization of the magnetic core. When an alternating voltage is applied to the primary winding, the magnetic field flux generated changes along the core, resulting in energy loss for hysteresis and eddy currents.

Hysteresis is the fact that the magnetic field in the magnetic core lags behind the change in the magnetizing current.

Eddy current is the phenomenon in which currents are generated in the core under the influence of an alternating magnetic field, which move along the core, heating it and causing energy loss.

Electrical losses (copper losses) - occur when the transformer operates under load. The losses in the winding constitute the main part of the electrical losses and are caused by the resistance of the winding. An increase in current causes the coil to heat up more, and according to the Joule-Lens law, the power dissipation in the conductor depends on the square of the current.

Additional losses - losses that occur in various metal parts of the transformer due to the scattering of the magnetic field, although these losses are small compared to the losses in copper, contribute to the total loss.

Factors affecting transformer efficiency.

Magnetic core structure: To reduce eddy currents, the plates are insulated and used in a multi-section form.

Core material: Modern materials with low hysteresis losses are used, which helps to reduce the net operating losses.

Coil material: Losses in the coil are reduced by using conductors with low resistance, for example, copper conductors.

Transformer load: Copper losses depend on the square of the current, therefore, it is necessary to correctly select the transformer power for a specific load.

In determining the efficiency of a transformer, there is also the concept of determining the F.I.K. energy, in which the energy supplied to the consumer during the year is W_2 (kW-h), and the energy received by the transformer from the network during this time

The ratio of W_1 (kWh) to W_2 can also be interpreted as $\eta = W_2/W_1$.

Calculation of transformer losses is a task for assessing efficiency and optimizing operating modes.

1. Electrical energy losses for a given period (ΔW_T)

$$\Delta W_T = \Delta W_0 + (\Delta W_{yuk} + \frac{\Delta W_T}{100})$$

ΔW_0 – net operating loss for a given period, kW

ΔW_{yuk} - relative load loss, %.

ΔW_T - full transformer power, kVA

2. No-load loss:

$$\Delta W_0 = \Delta P_0 * T_0 \left(\frac{U_1}{U_N} \right)^2$$

ΔP_0 – no-load power loss (kW)

T_0 – transformer operating time (s)

U_1 – actual voltage (V)

U_N – nominal voltage (V)

3.Relative load losses(ΔW_{yuk1}):

$$\Delta W_{yuk1} = \left(\frac{\Delta W_{yuk}}{\Delta W_T} \right) * 100$$

ΔW_{yuk} – load power loss (kW)

ΔW_T – transformer capacity (kVA)

Transformer F.I.K.

The transformer efficiency is the ratio of the active power supplied to the load to the active power received by the transformer from the network. The efficiency depends on the transformer loading and reaches its maximum value at 50-70% of the transformer's nominal power.

$$FIK = \left(\frac{P_{output}}{P_{input}} \right) \times 100\%$$

P_{output} – transformer output power,

P_{input} - transformer input power,

Conclusion

Unexpected power outages in power grids have major negative consequences. Therefore, providing consumers with uninterrupted, reliable and high-quality electricity is a constant problem. Power transformers play a key role in the transmission of electricity, so their efficiency is of great importance. By analyzing and identifying ways to reduce energy waste in transformers, their operating modes are optimized. Reducing waste not only helps to save resources, but also reduces the negative impact on the environment. Its efficiency and reliability are ensured by modern materials, optimization of the magnetic system and the correct selection of the transformer.

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